

**O‘ZBEK XALQ ERTAGINI BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFI
O‘QUVCHILARIGA O‘RGATISH USULLARI**

Mominova Yulduz Aminboyevna

Toshkent gumanitar fanlar universiteti assistent o‘qituvchisi

E-mail: ymominova7@gmail.com

Orcid: 0009-0002-5416-2032

Saparbayeva Shahnoza

Toshkent gumanitar fanlar universiteti boshlang‘ich ta‘lim yo‘nalishi talabasi

E-mail: Shahnozasoporboeva033@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: O‘zbek xalq ertaklarini o‘qitish, avvalo, bolalarning badiiy nutqini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Ertaklar orqali bolalar hayotda duch keladigan muammolarni hal etish ko‘nikmalarini egallaydilar. Ertaklar nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki axloqiy tarbiya beruvchi vositalardir. Ushbu maqolada O‘zbek xalq ertaklarini o‘qitish usullari va ularning ta‘siri haqida batafsil ma‘lumot beramiz.

Kalit so‘z: ertak, metod, xalq, boshlang‘ich, o‘zbek, rasm chizish, ijodkorlik.

**METHODS OF TEACHING UZBEK FOLK TALES TO ELEMENTARY
SCHOOL STUDENTS**

Mominova Yulduz Aminboyevna

assistant teacher of Tashkent University of Humanities

Saparbayeva Shahnoza

a student of elementary education at Tashkent University of Humanities

Abstract: Teaching Uzbek folk tales helps to develop children's artistic speech. Through fairy tales, children acquire skills to solve problems they face in life. Fairy

tales are not only educational, but also moral education tools. In this article, we provide detailed information about the methods of teaching Uzbek folk tales and their effects.

Key words: fairy tale, method, folk, elementary, Uzbek, painting, creativity.

Аннотация: Обучение узбекским народным сказкам способствует развитию художественной речи детей. Через сказки дети приобретают навыки решения проблем, с которыми сталкиваются в жизни. Сказки являются не только воспитательным, но и средством нравственного воспитания. В этой статье мы предоставляем подробную информацию о методах преподавания узбекских народных сказок и их эффектах.

Ключевые слова: сказка, метод, народный, элементарный, узбекский, живопись, творчество.

Introduction Uzbek folk tales are stories and narratives that are part of the cultural heritage of the Uzbek people and have been passed down from generation to generation since ancient times. They often represent the traditions, values, and aspirations of the Uzbek people. Uzbek fairy tales are mainly spread orally, and in most cases they are intended to educate students and teach them moral lessons. Uzbek folk tales are monuments that not only reflect the culture and traditions of the Uzbek people, but also play an important role in the spiritual and moral education of children. They have been passed down from generation to generation for centuries, full of life lessons, interesting stories and characters.

Fairy tales usually have heroes—faithful young men, beautiful girls, wise parents, or strong figures who fight evil forces. Also, animals play an important role in Uzbek folk tales. Fairy tales depict the behavior of animals as humans and teach them life lessons.

Uzbek folk tales are interesting not only for children, but also for adults, and through them universal human experiences and moral values are expressed. Through such stories, we remember the past and convey a great spiritual heritage to future generations.

Methods of teaching fairy tales are important in the educational process for children. Through these methods, children learn not only interesting stories but also moral lessons through fairy tales.

Teaching Uzbek folk tales, first of all, helps to develop children's artistic speech. Through fairy tales, children acquire skills to solve problems they face in life. Fairy tales are not only educational, but also moral education tools.

The following methods can be used in teaching Uzbek folk tales:

Story telling method:

One of the most effective ways to convey fairy tales to children is through storytelling. In this method, the teacher's voice, facial expressions and gestures play an important role. When the teacher tells a story in a caressing tone, the children listen attentively.

Interactive methods:

Children can be involved in the process through interactive methods. For example, by acting out characters or characters, children feel like they are part of the events.

Event Analysis:

After the story ends, it is also very useful to analyze the events. Asking children for their opinions about the actions of men, debating their heroics or shortcomings, develops critical thinking skills in them.

Drawing and creativity:

For children, inviting them to draw pictures or write their own version of the story will increase their creativity. This process will be interesting for them and will increase their interest in the fairy tale.

The following results are achieved when the methods of teaching Uzbek folk tales are chosen correctly:

- Children's attention level increases.
- Moral education will improve.
- Creativity skills develop.

- Interest in national culture increases.

Conclusion. Uzbek folk tales are an integral part of our rich culture, and it is very important to use modern pedagogical methods in their presentation. Within the framework of the ideas presented in this article, each teacher can use these methods in practice and expand the worldview of children. Every mother helps to realize this rich heritage, which is rich in the beauties of our country, and strives to pass it on to future generations.

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